

Temptation to Corrupt

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Prologue

The author was president of the well known Transparency International in Portugal region. In 1977 in this capacity, he established April 22 as a day to fight corruption, with the support of the Ministry of Finance and the Attorney General's Office.

A telephone line was opened for eight days - SAY NO CORRUPTION -, supported by the leading telephone operator.

One of the complaints received and forwarded to the Attorney General's Office concerned a Secretary of State for Justice, a judge who eventually bought a property in Porto for three times less. The author is a lawyer, has been a victim of professional persecution through a disciplinary case by the Portuguese Bar Association. The Bar Association considers it objectionable to encourage anonymous reporting of suspected corruption – case number I / 22/97, which applied to the author the sanction of CENSORSHIP.

Years later, a telephone line against corruption is now institutional in Portugal.

The Portuguese Bar Association continues to believe that any lawyer being an anti-corruption activist can be punished for not being worthy of his or her profession.

Here a shameful testimony about a corporatist organization that in Portugal understands that nothing should be done against corruption, which often involves its members.

Fundamental values

Identifying core values is the first step in creating a shared understanding in society regarding the expected behaviour of public office occupants.

Certain countries publish a list of core values to guide their civil servants in their daily operations, drawn from social norms, democratic principles, and professional culture.

The changing environment of the public sector requires the articulation of core values.

Many countries have updated their core public service values in recent years, and additional revisions are still being implemented. In the course of these revisions, countries have again emphasized "traditional" values, giving them modern

connotations and adding "new" values to reflect a results-based culture of public service.

For example, impartiality is the most frequently identified core value, implying equal access to public services as well as equality before the law.

Legislation on standards of behaviour has become the primary source of improvement of the core values indicated.

Almost all countries have developed a more detailed description of the expected patterns of civil servants in situations of potential conflict of interest, particularly regarding:

- Use of official information and public resources;
- Receiving gifts or benefits; and
- Work outside the public service.

In addition to the general standards applicable to all civil servants, the countries use supplementary guidelines for specific groups of professions related to sensitive areas e.g., high risk of conflicts of interest, such as those involved with law enforcement and tax administrations and customs.

Some countries have also developed codes for the conduct of government affairs by ministers.

Criminal laws penalize specific forms of corruption and deviations from fundamental values.

While almost all countries criminally punish active and passive acts of corruption by civil servants, an increasing number of states are also criminally punishing other forms of corruption, such as indirect corruption and attempted corruption.

Bribing a foreign public official is punished by an effective, proportionate and dissuasive way. A growing number of countries are also seeking to punish deviations from fundamental public service principles and values (such as impartiality in decision-making) and the use of public office for private benefit.

Public servants may ask for guidance from their superiors when faced with ethical dilemmas in the workplace. Some countries even offer access to specialized external bodies to ensure the neutrality of orientation.

Employee involvement - directly or through trade unions or professional associations in the review of values and standards, establishes a mutual understanding among public officials, and facilitates implementation.

The vast majority of countries ensure the transparency of their selection processes by publishing recruitment rules and vacancies. More than half of the states also consider ethical aspects in recruitment and performance appraisals.

Public procurement, and employ supplementary measures such as:

- Specific regulations and guidelines;
- Tighter control;
- Regular relocations of employees.

Disclosure of particular interests makes the decision-making process more transparent by minimizing the possibility of conflict between public office and private interest.

With few exceptions, countries require disclosure of personal financial interests, while half of the states also oblige employees to disclose whether they hold external positions and receive gifts.

The higher the position, the greater the transparency needed.

Disclosure of interests is typically required for elective positions and senior civil servants; some countries require it from civil servants in general.

Specific sensitive sectors, such as the tax and customs administrations, also rely on strict regulations requiring disclosure of interests.

- Establish punctuality standards;
- Request justifications for the decisions taken;
- Grant reparations to decisions;
- Require identification of conflicts of interest.

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Monitoring compliance Good governance of ethics not only sets standards of behavior but also monitors compliance.

Internal control is widely used to detect individual irregularities and systemic failures.

Countries have either reinforced existing legal mechanisms or established a legal apparatus for internal control. Internal control activities are conducted on an annual basis or as needed, recommending measures for better governance and, in some cases, report directly to the political level or the general public.

Internal control is accompanied by independent supervision.

This oversight forces public servants to be ultimately responsible for their actions to the public.

In virtually every country, the legislature is responsible for evaluating public sector activities.

Oversight range comes from independent external investigations by the Ombudsman or the Attorney General to specific judicial or ethical assessments.

Granting supervisory power to the independent Ombudsman has become a popular instrument of

More and more countries are designating a separate specialized unit to inspect the behavior of public servants.

Reporting misconduct by public servants is required by law and / or facilitated by administrative rules.

In most of these countries, too, there is a growing need to protect whistleblowers in the public sector. Almost half of these countries provide general protection, especially in the public service sphere, where available guarantees consist primarily of legal protection and anonymity.

It is providing citizens with conditions to report the misconduct of public servants.

Acting against misconduct, acting against standards violations is a shared responsibility between managers and external oversight agencies.

Disciplinary actions against lack of administrative decorum should be taken within the organization where such action occurs. All governments have developed a series of disciplinary procedures that allow managers to impose timely and fair sanctions or provide fair process guarantees to civil servants.

Administrative sanctions are warnings, reprimands, material penalties, temporary or permanent dismissal.

Also, countries have procedures and mechanisms that enable the public to report misconduct to supervisory bodies independent of public sector activities.

Citizens will trust public institutions if they realize that public agencies are used for the public good.

The lessons from the OECD survey suggest the following steps for building trust in public institutions:

- Define a clear mission for the public service

Adapting the public service mission to current needs and ensuring that core values and standards meet changing public expectations are major challenges for governments.

- Safeguarding values while processing changes

Changes in the socio-economic environment, especially the growing demand for transparency, require the government to review and adjust the mechanisms that ensure that civil servants' behavior meets expectations.

- Empower both civil servants and citizens to report misconduct
- Establish clear and recognized procedures that facilitate reporting misconduct and provide protection for whistleblowers who contribute to the detection of individual cases of misconduct.
- Articulate integrity measures in management as a whole

Integrity measures are not isolated activities but an integral part of all administrative systems in which integrity measures provide mutual support to the management environment as a whole.

- Coordination of integrity measures: a precondition for success.

- Successful integrity measures consist of a combination of actions that are consistent and take into account a broader public service environment.

Assessing the effectiveness of these measures provides policymakers with suggestions on their implementation and sets the stage for future policymaking.

- Change of emphasis from execution to prevention.

A good ethics management policy adequately combines enforcement and prevention measures.

However, there is a growing recognition that increased attention to prevention reduces the need for enforcement. Prevention is a less expensive investment in the long run, with a more favourable impact on public service culture and the relationship between public service and civil society.

- Anticipating problems

By anticipating situations that could weaken adherence to public service values and standards of behaviour, governments can prepare appropriate responses to prevent adverse effects from occurring. For example, how can governments address public demands for more information about private interests that affect public decisions?

- Exploring ways to harness new technologies enables governments to find new ways to internalize integrity and inform their citizens about expected standards of behaviour by public servants.

Common trends show that the following steps are needed to build a consistent system of support mechanisms, or, more specifically, the ethical infrastructure:

- Communicate and teach core values and ethical standards to provide clear guidance and advice in the process of resolving ethical dilemmas.
- Promote ethical standards by preventing situations that are conducive to conflict of interest and reward high standards of conduct through career advancement.
- Monitor compliance and report, detect, and discipline misconduct.

Bibliography

- Allen, N. and Birch, S. (2015) *Ethics and integrity in British politics: how citizens judge their politicians' conduct and why it matters*. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Andrei Shleifer and Robert W. Vishny (1993) 'Corruption', *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 108(3), pp. 599–617. doi: 10.2307/2118402.
- Bauhr, M. and Nasiritousi, N. (no date) 'Resisting Transparency: Corruption, Legitimacy, and the Quality of Global Environmental Policies', *Global Environmental Politics*. The MIT Press, 12(4), pp. 9–29. Available at: http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://muse.jhu.edu/journals/global_environmental_politics/v012/12.4.bauhr.html.

- Cooper, D. A., Kriekhaus, J. and Lusztig, M. (2006a) 'Corruption, Democracy, and Economic Growth', *International Political Science Review / Revue internationale de science politique*, 27(2), pp. 121–136. doi: 10.1177/0192512106061423.
- Cooper, D. A., Kriekhaus, J. and Lusztig, M. (2006b) 'Corruption, Democracy, and Economic Growth', *International Political Science Review / Revue internationale de science politique*, 27(2), pp. 121–136. doi: 10.1177/0192512106061423.
- Dahlstrom, C., Lapuente, V. and Teorell, J. (2012) 'The Merit of Meritocratization: Politics, Bureaucracy, and the Institutional Deterrents of Corruption', *Political Research Quarterly*, 65(3), pp. 656–668. doi: 10.1177/1065912911408109.
- Davis, C. L., Camp, R. A. and Coleman, K. M. (2004) 'The Influence of Party Systems on Citizens' Perceptions of Corruption and Electoral Response in Latin America', *Comparative Political Studies*, 37(6), pp. 677–703. doi: 10.1177/0010414004265879.
- Diamond, L. J. and Plattner, M. F. (1993) *The global resurgence of democracy*. Baltimore, Md: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Doig, A. (1995) 'Good government and sustainable anti-corruption strategies: A role for independent anti-corruption agencies?', *Public Administration and Development*, 15(2), pp. 151–165. doi: 10.1002/pad.4230150206.
- Donchev, D. and Ujhelyi, G. (2014) 'What Do Corruption Indices Measure?', *Economics & Politics*, 26(2), pp. 309–331. Available at: <http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/ecpo.12037/abstract>.
- Elklit, J. and Reynolds, A. (2005) 'A framework for the systematic study of election quality', *Democratization*, 12(2), pp. 147–162. doi: 10.1080/13510340500069204.
- Etzioni-Halevy, E. (1979) *Political manipulation and administrative power: a comparative study*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- E. Warren, M. (2004a) 'What Does Corruption Mean in a Democracy?', *American Journal of Political Science*, 48(2), pp. 328–343. doi: 10.1111/j.0092-5853.2004.00073.x.
- E. Warren, M. (2004b) 'What Does Corruption Mean in a Democracy?', *American Journal of Political Science*, 48(2), pp. 328–343. doi: 10.1111/j.0092-5853.2004.00073.x.
- Fisman, R. and Miguel, E. (2007) 'Corruption, Norms, and Legal Enforcement: Evidence from Diplomatic Parking Tickets', *Journal of Political Economy*, 115(6), pp. 1020–1048. Available at: <http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=buh&AN=31446547&site=ehost-live>.
- Goodwin-Gill, G. S. (1994) *Free and Fair Elections: International Law and Practice*. Geneva: Inter-Parliamentary Union. Available at: <http://ipu.org/PDF/publications/Free&Fair06-e.pdf>.
- Hamid Mohtadia, b., Terry L. Roza (no date) 'Democracy, rent seeking, public spending and growth', *Democracy, rent seeking, public spending and growth Recommended articles Download PDFs*, 87(3–4), pp. 445–466. doi: 10.1016/S0047-2727(01)00135-9.
- Hermet, G., Rose, R. and Rouquié, A. (1978) *Elections without choice*. London: Macmillan.
- Hyde, S. D. (2011) *The pseudo-democrat's dilemma: why election observation became an international norm*. Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell University Press.
- James C. Scott (1969) 'Corruption, Machine Politics, and Political Change', *The American Political Science Review*, 63(4), pp. 1142–1158. Available at: <http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://www.jstor.org/stable/1955076>.
- Klitgaard, R. E. (1988a) *Controlling corruption*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Klitgaard, R. E. (1988b) *Controlling corruption*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Magaloni, B. (2006) *Voting for Autocracy: Hegemonic Party Survival and its Demise in Mexico*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available at: <http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511510274>.

- Magaloni, B. (2010) 'The Game of Electoral Fraud and the Ousting of Authoritarian Rule', *American Journal of Political Science*, 54(3), pp. 751–765. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-5907.2010.00458.x.
- Marc Morjé Howard and Philip G. Roessler (2006) 'Liberalizing Electoral Outcomes in Competitive Authoritarian Regimes', *American Journal of Political Science*, 50(2), pp. 365–381. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-5907.2006.00189.x.
- McCoy, J. and Heckel, H. (2001) 'The Emergence of a Global Anti-Corruption Norm', *International politics*. Hague: Kluwer Law International, 38(1), pp. 65–90.
- Pelizzo, R. and Ang, B. (2008) 'A Code of Conduct for Indonesia: Problems and Perspectives', *Parliamentary Affairs*, 61(2), pp. 315–333. doi: 10.1093/pa/gsm064.
- Pellegata, A. (2013) 'Constraining political corruption: an empirical analysis of the impact of democracy', *Democratization*, 20(7), pp. 1195–1218. doi: 10.1080/13510347.2012.688031.
- Persson, A., Rothstein, B. and Teorell, J. (2013) 'Why Anticorruption Reforms Fail-Systemic Corruption as a Collective Action Problem', *Governance*, 26(3), pp. 449–471. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-0491.2012.01604.x.
- Persson, T. and Tabellini, G. E. (2003) *The economic effects of constitutions*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.
- Pharr, S. J. and Putnam, R. D. (2000a) *Disaffected democracies: what's troubling the trilateral countries?* Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Pharr, S. J. and Putnam, R. D. (2000b) *Disaffected democracies: what's troubling the trilateral countries?* Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Rose-Ackerman, S. and Palifka, B. J. (2016b) *Corruption and government: causes, consequences, and reform*. Second edition. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- in international perspective*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Rothstein, B. (2011b) *The quality of government: corruption, social trust, and inequality in international perspective*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Rothstein, B. and Uslaner, E. M. (2005) 'All for All: Equality, Corruption, and Social Trust', *World Politics*, 58(01), pp. 41–72. Available at: http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://muse.jhu.edu/journals/world_politics/v058/58.1rothstein.html.
- Sampford, C. J. G. (2006) *Measuring corruption*. Aldershot, Hants: Ashgate.
- Sandholtz, W. and Gray, M. M. (2003) 'International Integration and National Corruption', *International Organization*, 57(04). Available at: <http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://www.jstor.org/stable/3594846>.
- Sandholtz, W. and Koetzle, W. (2000) 'Accounting for Corruption: Economic Structure, Democracy, and Trade', *International Studies Quarterly*, 44(1), pp. 31–50. doi: 10.1111/0020-8833.00147.
- Schaffer, F. C. (2007) *Elections for sale: the causes and consequences of vote buying*. Boulder, Colo: Lynne Rienner Publishers.
- Vogl, F. and Dawson Books (2012b) *Waging war on corruption: inside the movement fighting the abuse of power*. Lanham, Md: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers. Available at: <https://www.dawsonera.com/guard/protected/dawson.jsp?name=https://idp.gla.ac.uk/shibboleth&dest=http://www.dawsonera.com/depp/reader/protected/external/AbstractView/S9781442218543>.
- Winters, M. S. and Weitz-Shapiro, R. (2013) 'Lacking Information or Condoning Corruption: When Do Voters Support Corrupt Politicians?', *Comparative Politics*, 45(4), pp. 418–436. doi: 10.5129/001041513X13815259182857.
- Yadav, V. and Oxford University Press (2011) *Political parties, business groups, and corruption in developing countries*. New York: Oxford University Press. Available at: <http://ezproxy.lib.gla.ac.uk/login?url=http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199735907.001.0001>.